

*New*ATHENA:

an European flagship X-ray
observatory

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XVI Reunión Científica SEA, Granada, 17 July 2024

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Advanced Telescope for High-Energy Astrophysics

- Second Large (L2) mission of ESA Cosmic Vision programme
- 2014 *Athena* selected: Science theme: The Hot and Energetic Universe:
- 2022-23 redefinition → *NewAthena*: flagship X-ray **observatory** designed to have seminal impacts across **many areas of astrophysics**

Athena: Advanced Telescope for High-Energy Astrophysics

The NewAthena X-ray observatory

Ariane 64 rocket
L1 orbit
5 years nominal mission
Proposal-driven observing program

X-ray Integral Field Unit

ΔE : 4 eV
Field of view: 4 arcmin
equivalent diameter
Pixel size: ~ 5 arcsec
Time resolution: 10 μ s

Mirror

Silicon Pore Optics
Collecting area: 1.0 m^2 at 1 keV
HEW: 9 arcsec on-axis
Focal length: 12 m

Wide Field Imager

ΔE : 160 eV at 7keV
Field of view: 40×40 arcmin²
Pixel size: 2.2 arcsec
Time resolution: 2 ms

Neutron Star Equation-of-State

Credit: S. Guillot (IRAP/Toulouse)

Fundamental science question

Constraining the Equation of State (EoS) of Neutron Stars (NSs)

Experiments

%-level radius in 2 rotationally-powered pulsars through pulse profile modeling

Key mission and WFI performance

WFI area, relative timing accuracy, area and NXB knowledge (calibration)

The second target [J0740+6620] yield $\delta R \sim 3-4\%$

Star-planet interaction

Credit: R. Osten (STScI).

Fundamental science question

Determine if and how stellar coronal activity (may) impact planet atmospheres

Experiments

Dynamics of stellar coronae, estimate of coronal mass losses

Key mission and X-IFU performance

X-IFU area and energy resolution

Spectral evolution of stellar flares in their own dynamical timescales (~ 100 s)

Also: X-ray spectroscopy needed to estimate full star spectral energy distribution

Particle acceleration in supernova remnants (SNRs)

Credit: L. Godinaud, A. Decourchelle, F. Acero (CEA).

Fundamental science question

Particle acceleration in SNR

Experiments

Determination of non-thermal (synchrotron) emission due to non-thermal accelerated e-

Key mission and X-IFU performance

X-IFU area, FoV, energy resolution

AGN feedback (quasar mode)

Fukumura et al., 2022, ApJ, 6, 940; simulation. Credit: P.O. Petrucci (IPAG), M. Dadina (OAS), G. Matzeu (ESAC).

Fundamental science question

Determine how powerful AGN outflow are launched and how they impact the evolution of galaxies

Experiments

Outflow spectroscopy to estimate energetics

Key mission and X-IFU performance

X-IFU effective area and energy resolution

Line profile dependence on outflow launching mechanism

Theory

X-IFU 200ks
Fe XXVI

Following the evolution of disk outflows on their dynamical time-scale becomes possible

AGN feedback (radio/mechanical mode) on the ICM

Credit: A. Simionescu (SRON).

Fundamental science question

Quantify how AGN feedback is dissipated into bulk motion and turbulence

Experiments

Spatially resolved turbulence determination on $\sim 10''$ ICM spatial scales

Key mission and X-IFU performance

Angular resolution, X-IFU area, NXB, energy resolution, and FoV

X-IFU/ACIS 100ks
 $10'' \times 10''$ resol element

Measurements at $100 \pm 20 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ level possible on ~ 8 systems ($\sim 1 \text{ Ms}$)

Map baryonic reservoirs: LSS filaments

Credit: I. Bartolucci (INAF IASF-Milano), E. Rasia (INAF-OATS) & F. Gastaldello (INAF IASF-Milano).

Fundamental science question

Map baryonic reservoirs, and probe their evolution and connection to the cosmic web

Experiments

Determine the morphology of large-scale structure filaments

Key mission and WFI performance

Angular resolution, WFI area, grasp, X-ray stray light

Simulations of a 14×100 ks WFI scan (1.7×1.7 degrees²) around clusters extracted from The300 simulations

4-5 out of 7 systems detected $>3\sigma$

[Caveat: no X-ray stray light yet. Exposure times to be optimised using priors from optical or eROSITA data]

NewAthena in context

Chandra (CXO)

XMM-Newton (ESA, D. Ducros)

XRISM (JAXA)

NewAthena

Effective area

- Mirror area: solution “15/13”
- The mirror structure retains 15 rows
- 13 rows are guaranteed to be filled
 - Deliver ~ 1.0 m² [mirror] area at 1 keV
- The two outermost rows will be filled if/to the extent costs and schedule permits

Full IFU (spatially-resolved) spectroscopy

NewAthena/X-IFU

XRISM/Resolve has 35 pixels (30'' side)

Credit: J. de Plaa (SRON).

WFI NewAthena effective area

Imaging

Large area and grasp are preserved

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NewAthena survey performance (WFI)

Number of Sources in a Single Pointing

AGN feedback

Credit: F. Carrera (IFCA), A. Georgakakis (NOA), L. Zappacosta (OAR).

Fundamental science question

Constrain the impact of quasar model feedback on galaxy evolution

Experiments

Measure the incidence and energetics of AGN outflows up to cosmic noon ($z \leq 4$)

Key mission and WFI performance

Angular resolution, grasp, WFI Non X-Ray Background (NXB), energy resolution

Survey allocation ($N_{\text{pointing}} \times T_{\text{exp}}$) to detect outflows in 10 AGN per redshift bin with $L_x = 10^{44.25-44.75}$ erg/s

Automatically achieved by the strategy fulfilling the AGN population science objective

NewAthena milestones

- Q4 2023: Re-started phase A
- Q4 2026: start Mission Adoption Review
- Q1 2027: adoption by SPC
- ...
- 2037 launch

Spanish participation

Athena Community Office

IFCA:

- * Scientific support
- * Communication
- * Outreach

Instrument development

- * SW algorithms on-board processing: co-I subsystem (**IFCA**)
- * XIFU consortium board (**CAB**)
- * XIFU Science co-I (**IFCA, CAB**)
- * XIFU Science Advisory Team (**CAB**)
- * XIFU Instrument Science Centre Team (Ground Segment) (**UA** Avisory Board, **IFCA**)
- * Athena simulator (**IFCA, UA**)

Scientific definition of the mission

- * NASST member (**ICE**)
- * Chairs WG (**IFCA + CAB**)
- * X-IFU science (**CAB, U. Alicante**)

Sensor development
INMA + ICMAB

Flight cryostat
AVS

Athena Community Office

- The *Athena* Community Office is supporting the *Athena* scientific community since June 2016.
- Currently, the community counts more than 1000 researchers spread around the world.
- Responsibilities:
 - Optimisation of the community efforts.
 - Organisational aspects.
 - Keeping the *Athena* community informed.
 - Developing communication & outreach activities.
- Led by IFCA (CSIC-Universidad de Cantabria) in Spain, with contributions from IRAP, MPE and University of Geneva

Web: www.the-athena-x-ray-observatory.eu

Twitter: [@AthenaXobs](https://twitter.com/AthenaXobs)

Facebook: [The Athena X-ray Observatory](https://www.facebook.com/TheAthenaXrayObservatory)

LinkedIn: [Athena X-ray observatory](https://www.linkedin.com/company/AthenaXrayobservatory)

E-mail: aco@ifca.unican.es

Outlook

- *NewAthena* will be a "flagship" X-ray **observatory**
 - With state-of-the-art optics and instrumentation
 - The community will decide through AO what to observe
 - Will impact virtually every corner of astronomy
- It will be an essential part of the observational landscape in the late 2030s together with ALMA, SKA, JWST, ELT, CTA, LISA, VRO, etc.
- Vibrant community supporting it
 - Watch out for new AO to join us!
- Key milestones:
 - Mission Adoption 2027
 - Launch 2037